

PREVALENCE OF INTESTINAL PARASITIC INFECTION AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN AGED 5-12 YEARS IN COMMUNITY PRIMARY SCHOOL GURE, KHANA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Intestinal parasitic infections are more prevalent among the poor sections of population. They are closely associated with low household income, poor personal and environmental sanitation, overcrowding, limitation and access to portable clean water, tropical climate and low altitude. Intestinal parasitic infections are the top global health problems whereas *Ascariasis*, hookworm, *Trichiuriasis* infections and *Amoebiasis* are among ten most common infections. The purpose of this study was to access the prevalence of intestinal parasitic infection among school children aged 5-12 years in Community Primary School Gure, Khana Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. This study was undertaken in Gure community from January to June, 2019. A total of 100 stool samples were randomly obtained using standard procedures and examined for the presence of parasites. The population for this study was children between 5-12years. A formal consent was obtained from the parents of each child/ward. The laboratory techniques involved aseptic collection of stool samples following standard quality procedure. Simple percentage was used for statistical analysis. Out of the total number examined, 10(10%) were found to be infected with one or more of the intestinal parasites. It also showed that out of the 10 positive samples, *Ascaris lumbricoides* was the most predominant:9(90%) and *Trichuris trichiura* was the least prevalence: 1(10%) Also, male children were more infected than the female children with 6(60%) and 4(40%) respectively. Statistically, it shows that 8(80%) of 5-8yearschildren were infected and 2(20%) of 9-12years children were also infected. Furthermore, intestinal parasitic infection was more prevalent in primary 1 3(30%), followed by primary 2 & 4 2(20%) and primary 3, 5 & 6 had the least prevalence1 (10%). Intestinal parasite is highly prevalent in this study area. The study concluded that provision of potable drinking water, adequate sanitary facilities, public education on personal hygiene and de-worming programme should be conducted in primary schools to reduce the prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections.